

ISic3451

Funerary inscription for Artemo

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Arianna Cinquatti,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2014.10.30 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

Mineo

Provenance

Territory of Mineo, probably contrada Favarotta

Coordinates

37.307741, 14.710805

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Mineo, Museo Civico Corrado
Tamburino Merlini, inventory 5197

Physical Description

A slab of regular form, although only the lower edge is finished.

Dimensions

Height 37 cm

Width 48 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Three lines of Greek text on the front of the slab

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

quadrate letters

Letter heights:

Not measured: mm

Interlineation

Not measured: mm

Text

1. Ἀρτεμοῖ
2. Χα[ρι]λλου
3. χᾶῖρε

Apparatus

Text after Cordano 2005

Translation (it)

Artemò, figlia di Charillos, salve

Translation (en)

Artemo, daughter of Charillos, farewell

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644927

Bibliography

Cordano, Federica 2005. Epigrafi. In Maniscalco, Laura(eds.), *Museo Civico "Corrado Tamburino Merlini" di Mineo: sezione archeologica*. Mineo. pp. 119-125.

At 123

Cordano, F. 2014. Materiale vecchio e nuovo dalla Sicilia orientale. In Alfieri Tonini, T., Struffolino, S.(eds.), *Dinamiche culturali ed etniche nella Sicilia orientale dall'età classica all'epoca ellenistica*. Trento. pp. 105-111. At 108 no.9

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3451. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358532>

Photo M. Metcalfe